

Multinomial Theorem on the Binomial Coefficients for Combinatorial Geometric Series

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Abstract: This paper presents a multinomial theorem on the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10, 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: computation, combinatorics, binomial expansion

1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea was stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-9]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-9] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

Binomial identities of V_r^n are given below:

(i). $V_n^n = 2V_n^{n-1}$.

(ii). $V_{kn}^{kn} = 2V_{kn}^{kn-1}$, ($n, k \geq 1$ & $n, k \in N$).

(iii). $V_{n-d}^{n-d} = 2V_{n-d}^{n-d-1}$, ($n > d \geq 0$ & $d, n \in N$).

(iii). $V_{n+d}^{n+d} = 2V_{n+d}^{n+d-1}$, ($n > d \geq 0$ & $d, n \in N$).

Proof for Binomial Identity (i):

$$\begin{aligned} V_n^n &= \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+n-1)(n+n)}{n!} = \frac{2n(n+1)(n+2)\cdots(n+n-1)}{n!} \\ &= \frac{2n(n+1)(n+2)\cdots(n+n-1)}{(n-1)!n} = \frac{2(n+1)(n+2)\cdots(n+n-1)}{(n-1)!} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Here, } V_n^{n-1} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)\cdots(n+n-1)}{(n-1)!}$$

$$\therefore 2V_n^{n-1} = V_n^n.$$

Proof for Binomial Identity (ii):

$$\begin{aligned} V_{kn}^{kn} &= \frac{(kn+1)(kn+2)(kn+3)\cdots(kn+kn-1)(kn+kn)}{n!} \\ &= \frac{2(kn)(kn+1)(kn+2)(kn+3)\cdots(kn+kn-1)}{(kn-1)!(kn)} \\ &= \frac{2(kn+1)(kn+2)(kn+3)\cdots(kn+kn-1)}{(kn-1)!} = 2V_{kn}^{kn-1}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore 2V_{kn}^{kn-1} = V_{kn}^{kn}.$$

For example, $2V_n^{n-1} = V_n^n$; $2V_{2n}^{2n-1} = 2V_{2n}^{2n}$; $2V_{3n}^{3n-1} = 2V_{3n}^{3n}$; for $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Proof for Binomial Identity (iii):

$$\begin{aligned} V_{n-d}^{n-d} &= \frac{(n-d+1)(n-d+2)(n-d+3)\cdots(n-d+n-d-1)(n-d+n-d)}{(n-d)!} \\ &= \frac{2(n-d)(n-d+1)(n-d+2)(n-d+3)\cdots(n-d+n-d-1)}{(n-d-1)!(n-d)} \\ &= \frac{2(n-d+1)(n-d+2)(n-d+3)\cdots(n-d+n-d-1)}{(n-d-1)!} = 2V_{n-d}^{n-d-1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore 2V_{n-d}^{n-d-1} = V_{n-d}^{n-d}$$

Proof for Binomial Identity (iv):

$$\begin{aligned} V_{n+d}^{n+d} &= \frac{(n+d+1)(n+d+2)(n+d+3)\cdots(n+d+n+d-1)(n+d+n+d)}{(n+d)!} \\ &= \frac{2(n+d)(n+d+1)(n+d+2)(n+d+3)\cdots(n+d+n+d-1)(n+d+n+d)}{(n+d-1)!(n+d)} \\ &= \frac{2(n+d+1)(n+d+2)(n+d+3)\cdots(n+d+n+d-1)}{(n+d-1)!} = 2V_{n+d}^{n+d-1}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore 2V_{n+d}^{n+d-1} = V_{n+d}^{n+d}$$

Theorem 2.1: $\frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!} = V_n^r$, where $n, r \geq 0$ & $n, r \in N$.

Proof. $\binom{n+r}{n} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!(n+r-n)!} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)}{r!} = V_n^r.$

That is, $V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)}{r!} = \prod_{i=1}^r \frac{n+i}{r!}.$

From the above expressions, we conclude that

$$\frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!} = V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)}{r!}, \text{ where } n, r \geq 0 \text{ \& } n, r \in N.$$

Theorem 2.2: $2 \frac{(2n-1)!}{n!(n-1)!} = \frac{(2n)!}{(n!)^2},$ where $n \geq 1$ & $n \in N.$

Proof. By applying Theorem 2.1 to $2V_n^{n-1} = V_n^n,$ we get that

$$2 \frac{(n+n-1)!}{n!(n-1)!} = \frac{(n+n)!}{n!n!} \Rightarrow 2 \frac{(2n-1)!}{n!(n-1)!} = \frac{(2n)!}{(n!)^2} \left(\because V_n^r = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!} \right).$$

Corollary 2.1: $2 \frac{(2kn-1)!}{(kn)!(kn-1)!} = \frac{(2kn)!}{(kn!)^2},$ where $k, n \geq 1$ & $k, n \in N.$

Similarly, we can constitute the corollaries for the following binomial identities

$V_{n-d}^{n-d} = 2V_{n-d}^{n-d-1}$ and $V_{n+d}^{n+d} = 2V_{n+d}^{n+d-1}$ such that

Corollary 2.2: $\frac{\{2(n-d)\}!}{\{(n-d)\}^2} = 2 \frac{\{2(n-d)-1\}!}{(n-d)!(n-d-1)!}$ and

Corollary 2.3: $\frac{\{2(n+d)\}!}{\{(n+d)\}^2} = 2 \frac{\{2(n+d)-1\}!}{(n+d)!(n+d-1)!}.$

Theorem 2.2 : For any k nonnegative integers n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots and $n_k,$

$$V_{n_1}^{n_2+n_3+n_4+\dots+n_k} \times V_{n_2}^{n_3+n_4+\dots+n_k} \times V_{n_3}^{n_4+n_5+\dots+n_k} \times \dots \times V_{n_{k-1}}^{n_k} = \frac{(n_1+n_2+n_3+\dots+n_k)!}{(n_1!n_2!n_3!\dots n_k!)}.$$

Proof. By applying ‘‘Theorem 2.1’’ for each term in the following combinatorial expansions

$V_{n_1}^{n_2+n_3+n_4+\dots+n_k} \times V_{n_2}^{n_3+n_4+\dots+n_k} \times V_{n_3}^{n_4+n_5+\dots+n_k} \times \dots \times V_{n_{k-1}}^{n_k},$ we can rewrite as follows:

$$\frac{(n_1+n_2+n_3+\dots+n_k)!}{n_1!(n_2+n_3+\dots+n_k)!} \times \frac{(n_2+n_3+\dots+n_k)!}{n_2!(n_3+n_4+\dots+n_k)!} \times \frac{(n_3+n_4+\dots+n_k)!}{n_3!(n_4+n_5+\dots+n_k)!} \times \dots$$

$$\times \frac{(n_{k-1}+n_k)!}{n_{k-1}!n_k!} = \frac{(n_1+n_2+n_3+\dots+n_k)!}{n_1!n_2!n_3!\dots n_k!}.$$

By simplifying the above expression, we get the following multinomial expansion

$$\frac{(n_1+n_2+n_3+\dots+n_k)!}{n_1!n_2!n_3!\dots n_k!}.$$

Now,
$$V_{n_1}^{n_2+n_3+n_4+\dots+n_k} \times V_{n_2}^{n_3+n_4+\dots+n_k} \times V_{n_3}^{n_4+n_5+\dots+n_k} \times \dots \times V_{n_{k-1}}^{n_k}$$

$$= \frac{(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)!}{(n_1! n_2! n_3! \dots n_k!)}.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

Conclusion

In this article, a multinomial theorem was built using the binomial theorem on the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers for research and development further.

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